

ORIGIN OF THE WORD QASAM IN ARABIC LANGUAGE

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Annotation: the purpose of the article is to analyze the use of the word (qasam) oath (n) and swear (v) in the Qur'anic surahs and its relations, i.e. negative and positive indicators.

Key words: Qasam (oath(n) and swear(v)), sura, Qur'an, positive, negative, emphasis, kalmia, word and phrase.

Introduction

Prepositions expressing an oath (qasam)(jar letters) : ب و ت

{تَنْطِقُونَ أَنْكُمْ مَا مِثْلَ لِحَقِّ إِنَّهُ وَالْأَرْضِ السَّمَاءِ فَوْرَبِّ}

So, by the Lord of the heavens and the earth, surely it (i.e., everything that is promised to you) is true just like your words (i.e., the words you speak are true for you). [Surat al-Zariyat: 23]

If in Arabic و an oath(qasam) is taken, it is obligatory to use the factor as a verb, that is, not to use the verb as the object of the factor: الله اق سم but الله و suffice it to say.

Also, belongs to و one of the features, after the noun comes, the pronoun does not come!

{الْفَيْمَةِ بِيَوْمِ أَقْسِمُ لَا}

Data collection and Analysis

1. I swear (qasam) by the Day of Judgment. [Qiyamat Surah: 1]

As for the letter ت the factor is added to this letter as well. This letter is used only with the words Allah and Rab, that is, the one who is actually swearing is mentioned.

{تَفْتَرُونَ كُنْتُمْ عَمَّا لُتْسَلْنَ تَأَلَّهِ رَزَقْنَهُمْ مِمَّا نَصَبُوا يَعْلَمُونَ لَا لِمَا وَيَجْعَلُونَ}

They spend from what We have provided for idols of which they do not know (i.e., whom they think are gods due to their ignorance). (O polytheists), by Allah, you will surely be held accountable (on the Day of Resurrection) for the idols you created. [Surah Nahl:56]

Sometimes a swear word is also used to describe someone's name, but it only appears in the sense of meaning: {الْجَحِيمَ لَتَرُونَ}

I swear (qasam) that you will see hell! [Surah Taksoor: 6]

{يَسِيرَ اللَّهِ عَلَىٰ وَذَلِكَ عَمَلْتُمْ بِمَا لُتْنَبُونَ ثُمَّ لَتُبْعَنَّ وَرَبِّي بَلَىٰ قُلْ يُبْعَثُونَ لَنْ أَنْ كَفَرُوا الَّذِينَ رَعَمَ}

Those who disbelieved claimed that they would never be resurrected. Say (O Muhammad peace be upon them): "No! By my Lord, you will surely be resurrected, and then you will surely be informed of what you did. This is easy for Allah." [Surah Taghabun: 7]

Words expressing an oath(qasam): لَأَيْمُنُ ، لَأَيْمُنُ ، لَأَعْرَكَ أَيْمُنُ ، These are divided into positive(+) and negative(-) Positive(+): أَنْ after this لَ and negative (-): words oath (qasam)

{تَحْكُمُونَ لِمَا لَكُمْ إِنَّ الْقِيَمَةَ يَوْمَ إِلَىٰ بُلْغَةَ عَلَيْنَا أَيْمُنُ لَكُمْ أَمْ}

Perhaps We have oaths (qasam) for you that will last until the Day of Resurrection, saying: "Undoubtedly, whatever you decide will be yours"?! [Surah Qalam: 39]

{يَعْمَهُونَ سَكَرْتِهِمْ لَفِي إِنَّهُمْ لَعَمْرُكَ}

(O Muhammad, may the peace and blessings of God be upon him), oaths (qasam) by your life, while they were wandering in their drunken state, [Surah Hijr:72]

{يَنْتَهُونَ لَعَلَّهُمْ لَهُمْ أَيْمُنَ لَا إِنَّهُمْ الْكُفْرَ أَيْمَةَ فَقَاتِلُوا دِينَكُمْ فِي وَطَعْنُوا عَهْدِهِمْ بَعْدَ مِنْ أَيْمَنَهُمْ نَكْتُوا وَإِنْ}

If after their covenant they break their oaths and throw stones at your religion,

By the night that comes and goes with its darkness; [Surah Takweer: 17] Negative

(-): {تَنْفَسَ إِذَا وَالصُّبْحِ}

And I swear by the dawn that [Surah Takweer:18] Negative(-): {بِالشَّفَقِ أَقْسِمُ فَلَا}

So, I swear by the dawn (which covers the whole horizon when the sun is setting);

[Surah Inshiqaq:16] Negative (-): {وَسَقَى وَمَا وَاللَّيْلِ}

By the night and (everything) it encompasses; [Surat al-Inshiqaq:17] Negative (-):

{أَنْسَقَى إِذَا وَالْقَمَرَ}

And I swear by the moon when it is full (i.e. the full moon) that [Surah

Inshiqaq:18] Negative (-): {الْبُرُوجِ ذَاتِ وَالسَّمَاءِ}

1. Oath to the sky, the owner of the constellations; [Surah Buruj:1] Negative (-):

{الْمَوْعُودِ وَالْيَوْمِ}

2. Oath on the Promised (Judgment) Day; [Surah Buruj: 2] Negative (-): {وَشَاهِدٍ

وَمَشْهُودٍ}

3. By the One who will witness (on that Day) and the One who will witness (all

events) [Surah Buruj:3]. negative(-): {وَالطَّارِقِ وَالسَّمَاءِ}

By heaven, by the night traveler, [Surah Tariq:1] Negative (-): {الرَّجَعِ ذَاتِ السَّمَاءِ وَ}

I swear by the sky, which is the owner of rain; [Surah Tariq:11] Negative (-):

{الصَّدْعِ ذَاتِ وَالْأَرْضِ}

(Because of that rain) oath by the Earth, the owner of the bursting (grain-dun,

grass-grass), [Surah Tariq:12] Negative (-): {وَالْفَجْرِ}

1. Oath to dawn. [Surah Fajr:1]. Negative (-): {عَشْرٍ وَلَيَالٍ}

2. Oath for ten nights (the previous one in the month of Dhul-Hijjah). [Surah

Fajr:2] Negative (-): {وَالْوَتْرِ وَالشَّفَعِ}

3. Oath to even and odd (rakat prayers). [Surah Fajr:3] Negative (-): {يَسْرٍ إِذَا وَاللَّيْلِ}

4. Oath by the passing night, (indeed the disbelievers will be punished)! [Surah

Fajr:4] Negative (-): {حَجْرٍ لِّذِي قَسَمَ ذَلِكَ فِي هَلْ}

5. Is there (enough) oath for the one who has a mind?! [Surah Fajr:5] Negative (-):

{الْبَلَدِ بِهَذَا أَقْسِمُ لَا}

(O Muhammad peace be upon him), to this city, [Balad surah:1] Negative (-):

{وَلَدٌ وَمَا وَالِدٌ}

And do not swear by the father and his children (that is, Adam and all his descendants). [Surah Balad:3] Negative (-): {وَضُحَلَهَا وَالشَّمْسِ}

1. Oath by the sun and its rain. [Surat al-Shams:1] Negative (-): {تَلَّهَا إِذَا وَالْقَمَرِ}

2. Oath by the moon that comes after it (the sun). [Surat al-Shams:2] Negative(-): {جَلَّهَا إِذَا وَالنَّهَارِ}

3. Oath by the day that He revealed (the sun to the world). [Surat al-Shams:3] Negative(-): {يَعْشَلَهَا إِذَا وَاللَّيْلِ}

4. I swear (qasam) by the night that it covers (the sun with its darkness). [Surah Shams:4] Negative (-): {بَنَلَهَا وَمَا وَالسَّمَاءِ}

5. Oath y the sky and the One who built it. [Surah Shams:5] Negative (-): {وَالْأَرْضِ وَمَا وَالسَّمَاءِ}

6. Oath by the earth and the One who made it flat. [Surah Shams:6] Negative (-): {سَوَّلَهَا وَمَا وَالنَّفْسِ}

7. To the soul and made it perfect, [Surah Shams: 7] Negative(-): {فُجُورَهَا فَالْهَمَهَا وَمَا وَالنَّفْسِ}

8. By the One who inspired and taught him both his debauchery and piety, [Surah Shams: 8] Negative(-): {يَعْشَى إِذَا وَاللَّيْلِ}

1. Oath to the coming night (with its darkness); [Surah Layl:1] Negative (-): {تَجَلَّى إِذَا وَالنَّهَارِ}

2. I swear by the shining day; [Surah Layl:2] Negative: {وَالْأُنْتَى الذَّكَرَ خَلَقَ وَمَا}

3. Oath by the One who created man and woman, [Surah Layl:3] Negative(-): {وَالزَّيْتُونَ وَاللَّيْلِ}

1. Oath by figs, by olives; [Surah Tayn:1] Negative(-) (-): {سَبِينِينَ وَطُورِ}

2. (God spoke directly to Prophet Moses) oath on Mount Sinai; [Surah Tiyn:2] Negative(-): {الْأَمِينَ الْبَلَدِ وَهَذَا}

3. Oath by this peaceful city (Makkai Mukarrama); [Surah Tayn:3] Negative(-):

{ضَبَّخًا وَالْعَدِيَّتِ}

1. Oath by the (horses) that gallop (in the way of Allah); [Surat al-Adiyat:1]

Negative (-): {قَدَّحًا فَالْمُورِيَّتِ}

2. Oath by those (horses) whose hooves flash lightnings (while running); [Surat

al-Adiyat:2] Negative(-): {صُبَّخًا فَالْمُغِيرَتِ}

3. An oath to the (horses) that rush (on the prey) at dawn; [Surat al-Adiyat:3]

Negative(-): {جَمَعًا بِهٖ فَوَسَطَنَ}

5. By the (horses) that enter the midst of the (enemy) team with this (dust); [Surat

al-Adiyot:5] Positive(+): {الْجَحِيمَ لَنَرُوْنَ}

6. You will surely see hell! [Surah Thakosur:6] Positive(+): {الْيَقِيْنَ عَيْنَ لَنَرُوْنَهَا ثُمَّ}

7. Once again I swear that you will see him clearly! [Surah Thakosur:7]

Negative(-): {وَالْعَصْرِ}

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that Qasam (oath(noun) swear(verb)) is a word that is used in the Qur'an first and foremost as an oath to God. Regardless of its relationship, the purpose of its use is the same, that is, one swears by God's creation only for the purpose of proof.

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